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D3.5 Policy Linking, Interoperability and Sharing v1

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Policy Indicator
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
CSV	Comma Separated Value
API	Application Programming Interface
NLTK	Natural Language Tool Kit

Executive summary

This deliverable is a demonstrator of the Policy interoperability, linking and sharing component in the AI4PublicPolicy platform, developed in WP3 “AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies”. Specifically, this component was developed in the context of task 3.3 “Cross Country Policy Interoperability and Sharing” and task 3.4 “Tools and Techniques for Policy Linking”. The deliverable presents the initial version of this component. The component implements the translation of policies and dataset definitions into different languages to favour the reuse of policies and datasets across countries with different languages.

A policy definition in the context of AI4PublicPolicy project has a concrete set of parameters which include name, area, objective, description, associated datasets and a set of Key Policy Indicators (KPI). Most of this information is in natural language. In this first version of the demonstrator KPIs, description and goals of different policies are compared and presented to the user, which is in charge of deciding if there is a relationship between two policies.

This component uses the information stored by the Datasets and Policy Management component described in deliverable D3.2 “Data Management and APIs for Data Collection V2”. This deliverable presents the usage, architecture and implementation of the first version of this component.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercialising the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform. The structure of the project in work packages is presented in Figure 1. This deliverable is the result of the work done in task T3.3 and T3.4 in Work Package 3.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of Work Package 3

WP3 *AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies* is a central work package in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. This work package provides the necessary components for: 1) enabling data collection and management of different types of datasets 2) Make data usable through interoperability techniques. 3) Enable reuse of datasets, policies, and AI models. 4) Contribute to openness through an open catalogue of policies, datasets and AI models.

1.3 Objective of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the first version of the software demonstrator for the Policy Linking, Interoperability and Sharing component developed in the context of tasks 3.3 Cross Country Policy Interoperability and Sharing and task 3.4 Tools and Techniques for Policy Linking. This software is in charge of doing the translation of policies and datasets schemas from the different pilots in AI4PublicPolicy and others that may be incorporated. The deliverable describes the architecture of the component, its subcomponents, how it is used and how the software is distributed.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** introduces the Policy Linking and Sharing component.
- **Section 3** is devoted to the description of the usage of the component presenting the different interfaces provided by the Policy Linking and Sharing component.
- **Section 4** presents the architecture of the component and its implementation, describing the subcomponents of the Policy Linking and Sharing, and the corresponding sequence diagrams.
- **Section 5** describes the Policy Linking and Sharing software distribution.
- **Section 6** presents the conclusions.

2 Policy Linking and Sharing

The Policy Linking and Sharing is in charge of doing the translation and linking of the policies and datasets definitions from different stakeholders in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. The component accesses the dataset management component for reading policies and datasets that need to be translated through the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME). This component can also be used independently of the VPME using the web interface of the Policy and Data Management component. Figure 2 shows the AI4PublicPolicy architecture and indicates the Policy Linking and Sharing component under the name “Cross Country Interoperability”.

Figure 2. AI4PublicPolicy architecture main components

3 Policy Sharing

In this section the functionality regarding the Policy Sharing component is presented. The component can be accessed from the web interface or using a REST API. The web interface is used by VPME users while the REST APIs are used internally for the integration with other components in the AI4PublicPolicy architecture, for instance with the AI4PublicPolicy Policies and Dataset Catalogue. Policies and Dataset schemas translated by the Policy Sharing component can be added to the AI4PublicPolicy platform by a user through the web interface of the Dataset and Policy Management component or through another component of the AI4PublicPolicy platform such as the Policy and Dataset Catalogue, implemented under task 3.5 “Searchable Catalogue of Policies and Datasets”, that allows importing policies and datasets from its interface to the Dataset and Policy Management using the REST API of the Dataset and Policy Management.

3.1 Web Interface

This web interface is used by the VPME users that are interested in different policies and datasets that are available but not in their mother language. The web interface offers translation of both the policies and dataset schemas from the language in which there were defined into another language. The policy sharing web is integrated with the Policy and Data Management web. This section describes the provided functionality.

Policies in a language

The policy web interface provides access to the different policies of a given area (Figure 3). Clicking on a given area (*Citizens and Business Services Optimisation* in the figure) all stored policies with their name, description, and associated datasets are listed. For instance, when the *Management and Optimisation of City Resources Area* is selected two policies are shown: *Optimized parking space allocation* and *Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes* (Figure 4). Just before the list of available policies, the language of the policies can be selected. By default, the policies shown are the ones defined in English.

Figure 3. Policies Interface

The translation of an individual policy is done by selecting the corresponding policy and selecting the target language. Immediately after the selection of the language all the associated information of the policy is displayed in that language.

Figure 4 shows the policies defined for the *Management and Optimization of City Resources* area: *Optimized parking space allocation* and *Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes*. Both policies were defined in English as can be seen in the drop-down menu of each policy description.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Policies

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: ----

Optimized parking space allocation [More information](#) Translate into english [Delete](#)

Identify on-street parking areas with high/low parking requests, so parking spaces between residents and guests can be allocated more efficiently to enable optimal use of space and high revenues for the City.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes [More information](#) Translate into english [Delete](#)

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets: Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Figure 4. Policies in English for the Management and Optimisation of City Resources Area

If a user searches for policies defined in a given language, she will select the language of the policies to be listed. Figure 5 shows the result of selecting Spanish language for the *Management and Optimization of City Resources* area. In this case, only a single policy is available in Spanish, the *Optimized parking space allocation* policy.

Figure 5. Policies in Spanish in the Management and Optimisation of City Resources area

Translation of a policy

The drop-down menu of each policy allows users to translate a policy into another language. Internally, the policy is translated, stored into a database and shown to the user. If the policy was previously translated, the translation step is omitted and the policy in the requested language has been translated previously. Then, the translation is retrieved from the internal database. Figure 6 shows the translation of the *Optimized parking space allocation* into Greek.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Policies

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: english

Optimized parking space allocation [More Information](#) Translate into greek [Delete](#)

Προσδιορίστε περιοχές στάθμευσης στο δρόμο με υψηλά/χαμηλά αιτήματα στάθμευσης, έτσι ώστε οι θέσεις στάθμευσης μεταξύ των κατοίκων και των επισκεπτών να μπορούν να καταναμηθούν πιο αποτελεσματικά για τη βέλτιστη χρήση του χώρου και τα υψηλά έσοδα για την πόλη.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes [More Information](#) Translate into english [Delete](#)

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Figure 6. Optimized parking space allocation policy translation into Greek

Finally, when the user clicks on the *More Information* button, the objective and the KPIs are shown in the same language as the police is. Figure 7 shows the objective and KPIs for the *Optimized parking space allocation* policy in Greek.

Home Policy Datasets XAI

AI4PublicPolicy
VPME

Policies

Areas

Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility

Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

Citizens and Business Services Optimisation

Management and Optimisation of City Resources

Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: english

Optimized parking space allocation [More Information](#) Translate into greek

Προσδιορίστε περιοχές στάθμευσης στο δρόμο με υψηλά/χαμηλά αιτήματα στάθμευσης, έτσι ώστε οι θέσεις στάθμευσης μεταξύ των κατοίκων και των επισκεπτών να μπορούν να καταναμηθούν πιο αποτελεσματικά για τη βέλτιστη χρήση του χώρου και τα υψηλά έσοδα για την πόλη.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes [More Information](#) Translate into english

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Optimized parking space allocation

Objective: Οι διαθέσιμες θέσεις στάθμευσης στην Αθήνα επισημαίνονται στο δρόμο και κατανομούνται μεταξύ κατοίκων της πόλης (απαιτείται ειδική άδεια) και επισκεπτών (πλήρωσιμη μέσω εφαρμογής στάθμευσης). Ως εκ τούτου, με αυτήν την πολιτική ο Δήμος Αθηναίων θα ήθελε να διαθέσει πιο αποτελεσματικά τους διαθέσιμους χώρους μεταξύ κατοίκων και φιλοξενομενών, ώστε να μην μένουν αχρησιμοποίητοι ή λείπουν χώροι κάθε εποχή.

Status: DEFINED

Name	Description
Ποσοστό κάλυψης θέσεων στάθμευσης	
Έσοδα από θέσεις στάθμευσης επισκεπτών	
Ικανοποίηση πολιτών	

Figure 7. Policy translation into Greek

Dataset schema translation

Datasets are defined in a given language, if the dataset format is either CSV, JSON or excel file, there are several named columns which may have a description of the information. This definition of the schema of the datasets can also be translated into different languages. The Policy Sharing component also provides the interfaces for doing this translation. Figure 8 presents the datasets available for the *Management and Optimization of City Resources* area.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Datasets

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

DATASETS

Dataset schemas in: ----

Wallet transactions This dataset contains all the transactions that the citizens or visitors execute with their digital wallet for parking services	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Parking transactions Purchases/activations that the citizens or visitors execute for parking tickets	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Incident management reports This dataset contains all the incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Incident management reports act This dataset contains all the activity history of incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Manutenzione attraversamenti pedonali Dataset with specific features for classify dangerous crossing road	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: xlsx

Figure 8. Datasets interface

By selecting the language from the *dataset schemas in* dropdown, all the available dataset schemas for the selected area and language are presented. Figure 9 shows the only policy defined in Spanish in the *Management and Optimization of City Resources* area.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Datasets

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

DATASETS

Dataset schemas in: spanish

Wallet transactions [More Information](#) Translate into spanish [Format: csv](#)

Este conjunto de datos contiene todas las transacciones que los ciudadanos o visitantes ejecutan con su billetera digital para los servicios de estacionamiento.

Figure 9. Datasets in Spanish in the Management and Optimisation of City Resources area

The translation of a schema is done by selecting the target dataset and language. Then, the dataset definition is shown in the target language. Figure 10 shows the translation of the *Wallet transactions* dataset schema into Italian.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Datasets

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

DATASETS

Dataset schemas in: [dropdown]

Wallet transactions Questo dataset contiene tutte le transazioni che i cittadini o visitatori eseguono con il loro portafoglio digitale per i servizi di parcheggio	More Information	Translate into	italian	Format: csv
Parking transactions Purchases/activations that the citizens or visitors execute for parking tickets	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Incident management reports This dataset contains all the incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Incident management reports act This dataset contains all the activity history of incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: csv
Manutenzione attraversamenti pedonali Dataset with specific features for classify dangerous crossing road	More Information	Translate into	english	Format: xls

Figure 10. Wallet transactions dataset schema translation into Italian

By clicking on the *More Information* button the fields of the dataset schema are shown in the language specified in the dropdown menu. Figure 11 shows the field description of the Wallet transactions dataset schema in Italian.

DATASETS

Dataset schemas in: ▼

Wallet transactions [More Information](#) Translate into Format: csv

Questo dataset contiene tutte le transazioni che i cittadini o visitatori eseguono con il loro portafoglio digitale per i servizi di parcheggio

Parking transactions [More Information](#) Translate into Format: csv

Purchases/activations that the citizens or visitors execute for parking tickets

Incident management reports [More Information](#) Translate into Format: csv

This dataset contains all the incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution

Incident management reports act [More Information](#) Translate into Format: csv

This dataset contains all the activity history of incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution

Manutenzione attraversamenti pedonali [More information](#) Translate into Format: xlsx

Dataset with specific features for classify dangerous crossing road

Wallet transactions

Schema			
Name	Type	Description	Default Value
Data di creazione	datetime	La data di creazione della transazione	
Tipo	string	Il tipo di transazione	
Tipo di servizio	string	Il servizio a cui è collegata questa transazione	
Importo	integer	L'importo della transazione	
Stato di successo	double	Lo stato della transazione	

Available Dataset Files

wallet transactions 2021.txt [Download](#)

Figure 11. Dataset schema translated into Italian

3.2 Policy Sharing REST API

The Policy Sharing component provides a REST API that may be used internally by other components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform. The REST API defined with Swagger is shown in Figure 12.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the Policy Sharing REST API. At the top, the Swagger logo and the API specification file path `/policySharing/openapi.json` are visible, along with an 'Explore' button. The main heading is 'Policy Sharing' with version '1.0.0' and 'OAS3'. Below this, there are links for 'Documentation', 'Contact the developer', and 'Apache 2.0'. A 'Servers' section shows the selected server as '/policySharing'. The API endpoints are organized into two sections: 'policy' (Policy translation operations) and 'dataset' (Dataset translation operations). Each endpoint is listed with its HTTP method, path, and a short description.

Method	Path	Description
GET	<code>/policies</code>	Returns all policies in a particular area and language
GET	<code>/policy</code>	Returns the policy information in the specified language
PUT	<code>/policy</code>	Translate a policy into a given language
GET	<code>/dataset/schema</code>	Returns the dataset schema in the specified language
PUT	<code>/dataset/schema</code>	Translates a dataset schema into a given language
GET	<code>/dataset/schemas</code>	Returns all dataset schemas in a particular area and language

Figure 12. Policy Sharing Swagger REST API

The operations for the policies are:

- **PUT /policy**
Translates a policy into a given language. Each policy has a unique integer identifier, *policy_id*. Figure 13 shows the operation definition where the *policy_id* and the target language are query parameters. If operation returns a value that indicates if the policy was already translated into the specified language or if it was translated. If the requested policy does not exist in the Policy and Dataset Management database, the operation returns an error.
- **GET /policy**
Retrieves the information of a policy in a given language. Figure 14 shows the operation definition where the *policy_id* and the target language are the query parameters. If the policy is available in the target language, it returns the policy definition in the requested language, otherwise returns an error message.
- **GET /policies**
Retrieves all policies in a given language and area. Figure 15 shows the description of the operation where the area and language are the query parameters. The operation returns a JSON object with all the policies available for that area and language. If the specified area or language is not supported an error message is returned.

PUT /policy Translate a policy into a given language

Translate a policy into into a given language

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
policyId * required integer (query)	The identifier of the policy to be translated Default value : -1
language * required string (query)	The language the policy will be translated Available values : spanish, greek, english, bulgarian, portuguese, italian Default value : spanish

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
	<p>Media type application/json</p> <p>Controls Accept header.</p> <p>Example Value Schema</p> <pre>[{ "code": 0, "message": "message", "type": "type" }]</pre>	
400	Invalid policy identifier value	No links

Figure 13. Policy translation operation REST API

GET /policy Returns the policy information in the specified language

Returns the policy information in the specified language

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
policyId * required integer (query)	The identifier of the policy Default value : -1
language * required string (query)	The language in which policy is searched Available values : spanish, greek, english, bulgarian, portuguese, italian Default value : spanish

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid policy or language	No links

Media type: application/json

Example Value | Schema

```
[
  {
    "area": "string",
    "dotsetsId": [
      0
    ],
    "description": "string",
    "id": 0,
    "kpis": {
      "name": "string",
      "value": "string"
    },
    "language": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "objective": "string",
    "owner": "string",
    "status": "string"
  }
]
```

Figure 14. Policy operation REST API

The screenshot displays the REST API documentation for the endpoint `GET /policies`. The description states: "Returns all policies in a particular area and language".

Parameters:

- area** (required, string, query): "The area of the policies". Input field contains "area".
- language** (required, string, query): "The language policies are searched for". Available values: spanish, greek, english, bulgarian, portuguese, italian. Default value: spanish. Input dropdown shows "spanish".

Responses:

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid area or language	No links

The 200 response includes a media type dropdown set to `application/json` and an example JSON value:

```
[
  {
    "policies": [
      {
        "area": "string",
        "datasetsId": [
          0
        ],
        "description": "string",
        "id": 0,
        "language": "string",
        "name": "string",
        "owner": "string",
        "status": "string"
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

Figure 15. Policies in area and language REST API

The operations that deal with the datasets are:

- **PUT /dataset/schema**
Translates a dataset schema definition into a given language. Figure 16 shows the operation definition where the `dataset_id` and the target language are the query parameters. The result indicates if the dataset schema was already translated or was translated. If the dataset schema does not exist in the Policy and Dataset Management database, the operation returns an error.
- **GET /dataset/schema**
Retrieves the information of a dataset schema in a given language. Figure 17 shows the operation definition where the `dataset_id` and the target language are the query parameters. If the dataset schema is available in the target language, the query returns the dataset schema definition in the requested language, otherwise returns an error message.
- **GET /dataset/schemas**
Retrieves all dataset schemas in a given language and area. Figure 18 shows the description of the operation where the area and language are the query parameters. The operation

returns a JSON object with all the dataset schemas available for the given area and language. If the area or language is not supported, an error message is returned.

PUT /dataset/schema Translates a dataset schema into a given language

Translates a dataset schema into a given language

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
datasetId * required integer (query)	The identifier of the dataset schema Default value : -1 <input type="text" value="-1"/>
language * required string (query)	The language the dataset schema is searched for Available values : spanish, greek, english, bulgarian, portuguese, italian Default value : spanish <input type="text" value="spanish"/>

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation Media type: <input type="text" value="application/json"/> Controls Accept header. Example Value Schema <pre>[{ "code": 0, "message": "message", "type": "type" }]</pre>	No links
400	Invalid dataset schema id or language	No links

Figure 16. Policy Sharing dataset schema translation operation REST API

GET /dataset/schema Returns the dataset schema in the specified language

Returns the dataset schema in the specified language

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
datasetId * required integer (query)	The identifier of the dataset schema Default value : -1
language * required string (query)	The language in which dataset schemas are searched for Available values : spanish, greek, english, bulgarian, portuguese, italian Default value : spanish

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid dataset or language	No links

Media type: Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schema

```
[
  {
    "area": "string",
    "description": "string",
    "id": 0,
    "imageFormat": "string",
    "language": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "owner": "string",
    "schemas": {
      "defaultValue": "string",
      "description": "string",
      "name": "string",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "sourceType": "string"
  }
]
```

Figure 17. Result of the dataset schema operation REST API

The screenshot shows a REST API interface for the endpoint `/dataset/schemas`. The interface includes a header with the method `GET` and a description: "Returns all dataset schemas in a particular area and language". Below the header is a "Parameters" section with two required parameters: `area` (a string query parameter with a text input field containing "area") and `language` (a string query parameter with a dropdown menu set to "spanish"). The "Responses" section shows a table with two entries: a 200 status code for a "successful operation" with a media type of `application/json` and an example JSON response, and a 400 status code for an "Invalid area or language".

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid area or language	No links

Figure 18. Result of dataset schemas in an area and language operation REST API

3.3 Implementation

3.3.1 Architecture

The Policy Sharing component is made of two main components: the policy and dataset translator and the Google Translate API. The policy and dataset translator component is a flask-python based server that implements the operations to translate policies and dataset schemas into a given language. The policies and datasets schemas must have been created using the Policy and Dataset Management component then, the Policy Sharing component access the Policy and Dataset Management database to read the policies and dataset schema definitions and for storing the translated ones persistently.

The translation is currently done using *Google Translate API*. This API provides a basic interface and an advanced one. The basic API includes the needed functionality for the Policy Sharing component. This interface includes methods for detecting the language of a text (*detectLanguage*), translating a text into a given language (*translateText*) and obtaining the languages that can be

translated from and into (*getSupportedLanguages*). The Policy Sharing is integrated with the Policy and Data Management web interface, which is implemented using HTML and JavaScript.

Figure 19 shows the Policy Sharing component architecture, its internal components and the interaction with the Policy and Dataset Management component, in particular with the Web Interface and the database (DB) and the Dataset and Policies Catalogue that import policies and datasets using the REST API provided by the Policy and Dataset Management component.

Figure 19: Policy Sharing component architecture

3.3.2 Data Translation

The translation of the policies and dataset schemas definition is done using the Google Translation Basic API. This API is provided in different languages such as Python, Java, Go and C#. Since the component is implemented using the flash python-based REST server, the Google Translation Python API has been used.

The Google Translation API requires to authenticate into Google Cloud. A service account JSON file with the credentials is generated. Then, the path to the file has to be stored in an environment variable, `GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS`¹.

```
export GOOGLE_APPLICATION_CREDENTIALS="/home/user/Downloads/service-account-file.json"
```

Next, the Google Translation Python library has to be installed and imported into the Python script to have access to the *translate_text*², *list_languages*³ and *detect_language*⁴ methods.

3.3.3 Data Persistence

Once a policy or the dataset schema has been translated into the desired language, it is stored into the Policy and Dataset Management database for future requests. This avoids repeating calls to the Google Translation API. Figure 20 shows the entity relationship diagram of the Policy and Dataset Management database used by this component. Tables in blue and green are some of the tables created to store the policies and dataset schemas definitions for the Policy and Dataset Management

¹ <https://cloud.google.com/translate/docs/setup?hl=es-419>

² <https://cloud.google.com/translate/docs/basic/translating-text?hl=es-419>

³ <https://cloud.google.com/translate/docs/basic/discovering-supported-languages?hl=es-419>

⁴ <https://cloud.google.com/translate/docs/basic/detecting-language?hl=es-419>

component. The grey tables are the new tables to store the translated policies and datasets definitions.

Both the TRANSLATED_POLICY and TRANSLATED_KPI tables have as primary key the policy identifier (POLICY_ID) and the language in which they are translated. The TRANSLATED_KPI table has also the KPI identifier (KPI_ID) as a primary key field (Figure 20).

The TRANSLATED_DATASET and TRANSLATED_FIELD tables store the dataset schema description, and the dataset schema fields name, and description into the requested language. In this case the TRANSLATED_DATASET table has as primary key the dataset schema identifier (DATASET_ID) and the translation language (LANGUAGE). The TRANSLATED_FIELD table has as primary key the field identifier (FIELD_ID), dataset schema identifier (DATASET_ID) and the translation language (LANGUAGE).

Figure 20: Policy Sharing database entity relationship diagram

3.4 Sequence Diagrams

This section presents the interaction between the different components using interaction diagrams when the Policy Sharing operations are executed.

Figure 21 shows the policy translation sequence diagram:

1. The user accesses the policy visualization web interface.
2. The user selects the area of the policies.
- 3-4. The user selects a policy and a language to translate the policy to.
- 5.1. The web interface sends a POST request to the Policy Sharing component.
 - 5.1.1. The Policy Sharing component retrieves the policy information in the requested language.
 - 5.1.1.1. If the policy information is empty the Policy Sharing component invokes the Google Translate service
 - 5.1.1.2. The Policy Sharing component stores the translated policy into the Dataset and Policy Management component database.

Figure 21. Translate policy sequence diagram

Figure 22 shows the sequence diagram for retrieving the policies in a given language:

- 1.The user accesses the policy visualization web interface.
- 2.The user selects the area to get the policies from.
- 3.The user selects the language of the policies.
 - 4.1. The web interface sends the GET request to the Policy Sharing component.
 - 4.1.1. The Policy Sharing component gets all the policies information available in the requested language and shows the policies in the policy visualization interface.

Figure 22. Policies available in a language

Figure 23 shows the dataset schema translation sequence diagram:

1. The user accesses the dataset visualization web interface.
2. The user selects an area for the dataset.
- 3-5. The user selects a dataset schema and the language.
- 5.1 The web interface sends the POST request to the Policy Sharing component.
 - 5.1.1 The Policy Sharing component retrieves the dataset schema in the target language and later shows the translated dataset schema in the dataset visualization interface.
 - 5.1.1.1 If the dataset schema has not been translated yet, the Policy Sharing component sends a request to the Google Translate service.
 - 5.1.1.2 The Policy Sharing component stores the translated dataset schema definition into the Dataset and Policy Management component database.

Figure 23. Translate dataset schema sequence diagram

Figure 24 shows sequence diagram for a request to retrieve the datasets schemas available in a language:

- 1.The user accesses the dataset visualization web interface.
- 2.The user selects the area.
- 3.The user selects the language for the dataset schemas
 - 4.1. The web interface sends a GET request to the Policy Sharing component.
 - 4.1.1. The Policy Sharing component retrieves all the dataset schemas in the requested language, and later shows the dataset schemas in the dataset visualization interface.

Figure 24. Dataset schemas available in a language sequence diagram

4 Policy Linking

The policy linking subcomponent is in charge of detecting policies that have similar goals, KPIs, definition or datasets. When a new policy is defined, the policy linking component searches for policies with similar KPIs, objectives, definition or datasets. A list of policies is shown to the user, who decides on the policies to be linked.

4.1 Web Interface

When a new policy is defined or updated the Policy Linking subcomponent searches for policies that may be related to the current policy under consideration. This relationship can be based on the goals, description, KPIs or datasets used.

Figure 25 shows the policy definition interface, as soon as the user modifies the description, objective, datasets or KPIs, the web interface detects the change and sends a request to the Policy Linking component that returns the candidate policies to be linked grouped by KPI, dataset, description or objective showing the candidates to the user. The user can select the policies to be linked with the new policy by clicking the link/unlink checkbox. When the user finishes the policy definition and clicks the submit button, the policy is sent to the Policy Management component that stores the definition into the database and into an index (Solr), and the linked policies are sent to the Policy Linking component that stores the linked policies into the Policy and Dataset Management database.

Home Policy Datasets XAI

Search

Search

Policy Definition

Register a new policy

Area

Policy Name

Owner

Policy description

Objective

Policy Datasets Add Dataset

SELECT THE DATASETS TO BE USED IN THIS POLICY

Dataset
 X

Indicate the dataset to be used in the policy from the available ones. This field can be empty and be filled latter.

Policy KPIs definition Add KPI

DEFINE THE KEY INDICATORS TO ESTIMATE FOR THIS POLICY

KPI #1

Name

Description
 X

Candidate policies Filter by: Description Objective Datasets KPIs

Description		Candidate policies		
Area	Name	Objective	Link / Unlink	
Energy Management	PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon	To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
KPIs				
kpi: Installed capacity (MWp)				
Area	Name	Objective	Link / Unlink	
Energy Management	PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon	To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Submit

Figure 25. Policy definition with candidate policies to be linked

Figure 26 presents the update of the policy *PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Madrid* and the list of possible policies to be linked once the policy has been updated. In this case five policies are candidates to be linked. Two of them were linked during the policy definition (checked checkbox in the candidate policies). The other two are proposed as candidates and the user can click on the link/unlink checkbox to link the policies. The words that link the policies are highlighted in the candidate policies. When the user clicks on the submit button the relationship is established and shown in further interactions with the policy.

Home Policy Datasets XAI

Search

Search

Policy Update

Update a policy

Area

Politic name

Owner

Policy description

Policy objective

Policy datasets
 DATASETS USED IN THE POLICY Add Dataset

Policy KPIs
 KPIS OF THE POLICY Add KPI

Related policies Filter by: Description Objective Datasets KPIs

Candidate policies

Description	Area	Name	Objective	Link / Unlink
	Energy Management	PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon	To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Management and Optimisation of City Resources	Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes	Have a reliable forecast of maintenance incidents in the coming months, or per season, to plan more efficiently the purchase or consumables and to plan for seasonal personnel hiring or allocation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Citizens and Business Services Optimisation	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	To determine the danger index of the city areas for vulnerable categories in relation to possible causes to decide and justify interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects	<input type="checkbox"/>

Objective	Area	Name	Objective	Link / Unlink
	Energy Management	PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon	To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

KPIs	Area	Name	Objective	Link / Unlink
kpi: Capacity (MWp)	Energy Management	PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon	To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Submit

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Figure 26. Policy update with candidate liked policies

When this policy is selected afterwards, all the information of the policy is presented including the three policies linked in the previous step (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Policy visualization

4.2 Policy Linking REST API

The Policy Linking component provides a REST API interface with all the operations available provided by the component. Figure 28 shows the Swagger definition of the Policy Linking REST API.

Figure 28. Policy Linking REST API

There are four operations that return the list of candidate policies to be linked with a given one, link two policies, get linked policies and delete linked policies. The operations are:

- GET `policyLinking/candidateLinkedPolicies/{policy_id}`
The operation returns a JSON object with all candidate policies and the common field (description, objective, datasets or KPI) and the words that match. If the requested policy is not available in the Policy and Dataset Management database, the operation returns an error. Figure 29 shows the definition of this operation.
- POST `policyLinking/{policy_id}`
Links two policies indicating the field that links the two policies. Figure 30 presents the operation parameters, which include an integer that represents the field that links the policy (-1 matches the description, -2 objective, -3 linked by the dataset, >0 linked by a KPI) and the list of common terms.
- GET `policyLinking/{policy_id}`
Figure 31 shows the description of the operation that returns the list of linked policies classified by the reason (description, objective, datasets or kpi) and the linked_words. This operation only requires the `policy_id` as path parameters and returns an error if the required policy is not available in the Policy and Dataset Management component database.
- DELETE `policyLinking/{policy_id}`
This operation deletes all policies linked to a policy or deletes a particular linked policy. It returns an error if the policy is not available in the Policy and Dataset Management. Figure 32 shows the details of the delete operation.

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GET /candidateLinkedPolicies/{policyId} All candidate policies to be linked

Returns the candidate policies to be linked with a given policy

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
policyId * required integer (\$int64) (path)	ID of policy

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid ID supplied	No links
404	Policy not found	No links

Media type: Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schema

```
{
  "description": [
    {
      "area": "string",
      "id": 0,
      "name": "string",
      "objective": "string"
    }
  ],
  "id": 10,
  "kpis": [
    {
      "id": 0,
      "name": "string",
      "policies": [
        {
          "area": "string",
          "id": 0,
          "name": "string",
          "objective": "string"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "objective": [

```

Figure 29. Policy Linking candidate policies REST API

POST /linkedPolicies/{policyId} Links policies with a given policy

Adds the policies as linked policies of a given policy

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
policyId * required integer(\$int64) (path)	ID of policy <input type="text" value="policyId"/>
linked_policy * required integer(\$int64) (query)	The policy to be linked with the given policy <input type="text" value="linked_policy"/>
reason * required integer(\$int64) (query)	The field that links two policies (-1: description, -2 objective, -3 dataset, >0 kpi id) <input type="text" value="reason"/>
linked_words * required string (query)	The list of words or dataset identifiers that share both policies <input type="text" value="linked_words"/>

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation Media type: <input type="text" value="application/json"/> Controls Accept header: Example Value Schema <pre>{ "code": 0, "message": "message", "type": "type" }</pre>	No links
405	Invalid input	No links

Figure 30. Linking two policies REST API

GET /linkedPolicies/{policyId} Linked policies

Returns all linked policies with a given policy

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
policyId * required integer(\$int64) (path)	ID of policy

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	successful operation	No links
400	Invalid ID supplied	No links
404	Policy not found	No links

Media type: Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schema

```

{
  "description": [
    {
      "area": "string",
      "id": 0,
      "name": "string",
      "objective": "string"
    }
  ],
  "id": 10,
  "kpis": [
    {
      "id": 0,
      "name": "string",
      "policies": [
        {
          "area": "string",
          "id": 0,
          "name": "string",
          "objective": "string"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "objective": "string"
}
    
```

Figure 31. Get linked policies REST API

Figure 32. Delete linked policy REST API

4.3 Policy Linking Implementation

The main subcomponents the Policy Linking is made from a natural language processing component, an index store and the Dataset and Policy management component. This section presents the architecture and implementation of the Policy Linking component and its integration with the Policy and Dataset management component.

4.3.1 Policy Linking Architecture

The Policy Linking component is composed of three main components: the Policy Linking server and an index and search engine, Solr⁵. The Policy Linking server subcomponent is implemented by the flask python-based server that provides the required operations to find policy candidates and linking policies. Figure 33 presents the Policy Linking architecture and the interaction with the Policy and Dataset Management component.

The Policy Linking subcomponent processes the policies which are defined in natural language. So this component uses a toolkit for natural language processing. Currently the NLTK⁶ toolkit is used for processing the definition of policies. NLTK provides a set of libraries for classification, tokenization, parsing and semantic reasoning of text in Python. When a policy is updated or defined, the different sections of the policy are parsed and tokenized. Only nouns and verbs are taken into account in the search for candidate policies to be linked.

⁵ <https://solr.apache.org/>

⁶ <https://www.nltk.org/>

Policies are stored in a distributed search server, Solr⁷, when they are defined. The definition of a policy is a JSON document that is stored as a Solr document. Solr supports different languages and multilingual searches in a document. For each token in the new or updated policy, a search is done in Solr in the corresponding section of previously defined policies. The documents matching the search are the ones retrieved and presented to the user as candidate policies to be linked. The information of linked policies is stored in the Policy and Dataset Management component, more concretely, in a table with the two policies and the reason for the linking (KPI, dataset, objective, definition). The link of two policies is removed when a policy is updated, and the link is deselected.

Figure 33. Policy Linking architecture

4.3.2 Data Persistence

The Policy Linking component persists the data in the Dataset and Policy Management database component and Solr.

4.3.2.1 Solr persistence

Solr provides a REST API to create collections, define schemas, upload and query documents. A collection is a single logical index that groups all documents with the same schema. Figure 34 shows a POST request to create a new collection with only one shard and one replica factor. When Solr is

⁷ <https://solr.apache.org/>

executed in cloud mode, the collections can be split into several shards and distributed among the nodes available in the cluster. The shards can be replicated for fault tolerance purposes.

```

1  curl --location --request POST 'http://'${SOLR_URL}.'/api/collections' \
2  --header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
3  --data-raw '{
4  |   "create": {
5  |     "name": "'${MY_NEW_SCHEMA}'",
6  |     "numShards": 1,
7  |     "replicationFactor": 1
8  |   }
9  | }'
```

Figure 34. Solr POST request to create a new collection

Figure 35 shows the schema definition to store the policies, which includes the policy identifier, description, objective, datasets and KPIs. If the field is indexed, this field can be used in queries to retrieve documents.

```

1  curl --request POST \
2  --url http://'${SOLR_URL}.'/api/collections/'${MY_NEW_SCHEMA}.'/schema' \
3  --header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
4  --data '{
5  |   "add-field": [
6  |     {
7  |       "name": "id",
8  |       "type": "pint",
9  |       "indexed": true
10 |     },
11 |     {
12 |       "name": "description",
13 |       "type": "text_general",
14 |       "indexed": true
15 |     },
16 |     {
17 |       "name": "objective",
18 |       "type": "text_general",
19 |       "indexed": true
20 |     },
21 |     {
22 |       "name": "datasetsId",
23 |       "type": "pint",
24 |       "indexed": true,
25 |       "multiValued": true
26 |     },
27 |     {
28 |       "name": "kpi",
29 |       "type": "text_general",
30 |       "indexed": true,
31 |       "multiValued": true
32 |     }
33 |   ]
34 | }'
```

Figure 35. Solr POST request to define collection schema for policies

Once the schema has been defined, documents can be uploaded. Documents in Solr are JSON files and can be loaded one by one or several in a single request. Figure 36 shows an example of a policy document upload request. This process is done by the Policy and Dataset Management component when a new policy is defined.

```

1  curl --request POST \
2  --url 'http://localhost:8983/api/collections/policyLinking/update' \
3  --header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
4  --data ' [
5  {
6  |   "id": 4,
7  |   "objective": "To determine the danger index of the city areas for vulnerable categories
8  |   "description": "According to the National Road Safety Plan, coherent with the \"Safe S
9  |   "datasetsId": [1, 4],
10 |   "kpi": [
11 |       "road death rate",
12 |       "road injury index",
13 |       "total coast for road traffic accidents with personal injury",
14 |       "accident frequency",
15 |       "road death risk",
16 |       "road injury risk",
17 |       "road injury cost"
18 |   ]
19 | }
20 ]

```

Figure 36. Solr POST request to upload a document

Each time a new policy document is uploaded, it must be indexed. A commit request is needed to make the document available. Figure 37 shows this POST request.

```

1  curl -X POST -H 'Content-type: application/json'
2  -d '{"set-property":{"updateHandler.autoCommit.maxTime":15000}}'
3  http://${SOLR_URL}/api/collections/${MY_NEW_SCHEMA}/config

```

Figure 37. Solr POST request commit documents

Figure 38 shows a Solr query that returns the stored documents that have the word “monitor” in the objective of the policy definition. In this case there is only one indexed policy document that satisfies the query condition.

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```
● aazqueta@MacBook-Pro-de-Ainhua bin % curl "http://localhost:8983/solr/policyLinking/select?indent=on&q=objective:monitor"
{
  "responseHeader":{
    "zkConnected":true,
    "status":0,
    "QTime":118,
    "params":{
      "q":"objective:monitor",
      "indent":"on"}},
  "response":{"numFound":1,"start":0,"numFoundExact":true,"docs":[
    {
      "id":"11",
      "name":"PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon",
      "area":"Energy Management",
      "objective":["To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization."],
      "owner":"LIS",
      "description":["Lisboa Cidade Solar® (Lisbon Solar City) strategy is part of Lisbon Climate Action Plan 2030, contributing to the city decarbonisation goals with 103 MW installed photovoltaic (PV) capacity target by 2030. Given that presently the city has only 8 MW installed PV capacity (official numbers, although there's slightly more), the Action Plan develops along two major vectors – municipal and private end-use sectors. Due to the unavailability of up-to-date and detailed information about Lisbon's existing solar energy systems, the city is unable to track its progress in relation its 2030 goals. Thus, this policy aims at establishing a data-based decision making for targeted implementation of PV in the city buildings."],
      "language":"en",
      "status":"NEW",
      "kpis":["Number of installations",
        "Number of panels",
        "Installed capacity (MWp)",
        "Installed capacity versus theoretical potential",
        "% of achievement of 2030 goal (103 MWp)"],
      "_version_":1758380041401532416}}
  ]}
}
```

Figure 38. Solr query example

4.3.2.2 Policy linking persistence

Once the user has selected the policies to be linked, the Policy Linking component stores the linked policies into the Policy and Dataset Management component database. A new table has been defined, LINKED_POLICIES (Figure 39). This table has as primary key fields POLICY_ID, LINKED_POLICIES and REASON. The REASON field can be set to -1 if the link is in the description, -2 if the reason is the objective, -3 if the reason is the dataset and a positive integer in case the link is due to a common KPI.

Figure 39. Policy Linking database entity relationship diagram

4.4 Policy Linking Sequence Diagrams

This section presents the sequence diagrams that define the interaction between the user and the different components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform that interact with the policy linking: policy definition, policy update and policy visualization scenarios.

Figure 40 shows the sequence diagram when a user defines a new policy.

1. The user accesses the policy definition interface.
- 2-9. The user fills the policy information: area, policy name, owner, language, policy description, the objective, datasets and KPIs.
10. The related policies are shown, and user selects the policies to be linked.
11. The user clicks the submit button and the request is submitted to the Policy and Data Management Component:
 - 11.1. A policy object is created.
 - 11.2 A POST request with the policy object to the Policy Management subcomponent is sent.
 - 11.2.1 – 11.2.2. The Policy and Dataset Management component store the policy in the database and in Solr.
 - 11.3. The web interface creates the policy sharing object.

11.4. The web interface sends the POST request with the policy sharing object to the Policy Sharing subcomponent.

11.4.1 The policy sharing stores the linked policies into the database.

D3.5 Policy Linking, Interoperability and Sharing V1

Figure 40. Policy Linking sequence diagram

Figure 41 shows the sequence diagram for updating a policy.

1. The user accesses the policy update interface.
- 2-3. The user indicates the area and the policy name.
4. The web interface retrieves the policy information, the policy candidates and the linked policies. The web is filled with the policy definition.
- 5-10. The user updates the fields owner, language, policy description, objective, datasets and KPIs.
11. The user selects the policies to be linked.
12. The user clicks the submit button and the request is submitted and send to the Policy Management Component:
 - 12.1. The web interface creates the policy object.
 - 12.2 The web interface sends a POST request with the policy object to the Policy Management component.
 - 12.2.1 – 11.2.2. The Policy and Dataset Management component and updates the policy in the database and into Solr.
 - 12.3. The web interface creates the policy sharing object.
 - 12.4. The web interface sends the POST request with the policy sharing object to the Policy Sharing subcomponent.
 - 12.4.1 The policy Sharing component updates the linked policies in the database.

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Figure 41. Linked policies update sequence diagram

Figure 42 shows the sequence diagram for the Policy Visualization.

1. The user accesses the policy visualization interface.
2. The user indicates the area of the policies.
3. The policies are retrieved, and the interface is filled with the basic (policy name and description) information of all policies in that area.
4. The user selects a policy.
- 5.1. The web interface fills the interface with the policy objectives and description KPIs of the selected policy.
- 5.2 - 5.3. The web interface gets the linked policies and fills the interface with the actual linked policies.

Figure 42. Linked policies visualization sequence diagram

5 Policy Sharing and Linking Software Distribution

The Policy Sharing and Linking components are distributed using Docker images that can be deployed locally using Docker for testing purposes or distributed using Kubernetes. Both components are integrated with the Dataset and Policy Management component, therefore the Policy Sharing and Linking components have to be in the same Docker instance or Kubernetes cluster and configure the network as the one used by the Dataset and Policy Management component.

The AI4PublicPolicy GitLab repository is private so credentials are required to access the repository and the AI4PublicPolicy Gitlab registry.

- Docker configuration

To deploy the Docker version of the components the user has to log in the AI4PublicPolicy Gitlab registry using the `docker login registry.gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/${project_path}` command that will request the user and password credentials.

- Kubernetes configuration

To deploy the Kubernetes version the user needs a Kubernetes Secret:

```
kubectl create secret docker-registry regcred --docker-server=<your-registry-server> --docker-username=<your-name> --docker-password=<your-password> --docker-email=<your-email>
```

5.1 Policy Sharing Software Distribution

The Policy Sharing project is available in the Gitlab repository of the AI4PublicPolicy project (<https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing>). Developers can download the source code of the project by cloning the repository to make changes and perform local testing. To deploy the component there are two different ways depending on the purposes:

- Testing purposes: Docker version
- Production purposes: Kubernetes version

For both options a docker image of the policy sharing component is needed and available in the Gitlab registry repository of the AI4PublicPolicy project:

https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing/container_registry.

5.1.1 Docker Container

The user can deploy the policy sharing component in a docker distribution using the image provided in the gitlab registry repository. The container can be executed through the docker run command or using the docker-compose.yml file available in the Gitlab repository:

- Docker run command:

To run the container using the docker run command execute the following command:

```
$ docker run -d -p 54747:8080 -e DB_HOST=${DB_HOST_IP_PORT} -e DB_USER=${DB_HOST_USER} -e DB_PSWD=${DB_HOST_IP_PSWD} -e DB_NAME="POLICY" --network=dataset-policy-management --name policy-sharing registry.gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing:1.0.0
```

- Docker-compose.yml

To run the container using the docker-compose command follow the next steps:

1. Download the docker-compose.yaml available in the Gitlab repository (Figure 43): <https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing/-/blob/main/docker/docker-compose.yml>

Figure 43. Policy Sharing docker-compose.yaml file

2. Execute the docker compose command:

```
$ docker-compose up -d
```

Both deployment ways start the policy sharing service as show in Figure 44, it is available at: <http://localhost:57457/policySharing/ui>

Figure 44. Docker version Policy Sharing REST API

5.1.2 Kubernetes version

To deploy the Policy Sharing component in a Kubernetes cluster the user has to download the Kubernetes manifest files available in the project gitlab repository. Files can be downloaded one by one from the project Gitlab repository, <https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing/-/tree/main/kubernetes>, or cloning the project repository.

```
$ git clone https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing.git
$ cd policysharing/kubernetes
```

First, the Kubernetes secret has to be created for the Policy Sharing Gitlab registry executing the following command:

```
$ kubectl create secret docker-registry ai4pp-policysharing-secret --docker-
server=registry.gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.3/policysharing
--docker-username=<your-name> --docker-password=<your-pword> --docker-
email=<your-email>
```

Next the user has to configure the Dataset and Policy Management database environment variables in the policy-sharing-deployment.yaml file and create the deployment Kubernetes object using the policy-sharing-deployment.yaml file:

```
$ kubectl apply -f policy-sharing-deployment.yaml
```

Run the following commands to check the status of the deployment and the pod created:

```
$ kubectl get deployment | grep policy-sharing
$ kubectl get pods -o wide | grep policy-sharing
```

The expected output has to be something similar to:

```
$ kubectl get deployment | grep policy-sharing
policy-sharing          1/1      1          1          6m40s
$ kubectl get pods -o wide | grep policy-sharing
policy-sharing-6485668767-tjzm7          1/1      Running    0
6m46s  10.150.1.150  blade147  <none>    <none>
```

The Policy Sharing service is running at host blade147.

Last, to access the Policy Sharing interface from outside the Kubernetes cluster is required to create a service:

```
$ kubectl expose deployment policy-sharing --type=NodePort --name=policy-sharing-
service
```

To check the service run the following command:

```
$ kubectl get services | grep policy-sharing
```

The expected output has to be similar to:

```
$ kubectl get services | grep policy-sharing
policy-sharing-service          NodePort    10.107.32.28  <none>
8080:31459/TCP                 10m
```

The Policy Sharing REST API port 8080 is exposed at port 31459 of the blade147 (192.168.1.247) host. As Figure 45 shows the Policy Sharing swagger REST API is available at <http://192.168.1.247:31459/policySharing/ui/>

Figure 45. Kubernetes version Policy Sharing REST API

5.2 Policy Linking Software Distribution

The policy linking project is available in the gitlab repository of the AI4PublicPolicy project (<https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking>). The source code of the project can be obtained by cloning the repository to make changes and perform local testing. To deploy the component there are two different ways depending on the purposes:

- Testing purposes: Docker version
- Production purposes: Kubernetes version

As well as the Policy Sharing component, the docker image of the policy linking component is available in the gitlab registry repository of the AI4PublicPolicy project: https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking/container_registry.

5.2.1 Docker version

The docker version of the Policy Linking component is intended for testing purposes. In this case, two different images are going to be used, one for Solr⁸ and the other for the Policy Linking component. Both components are deployed and configured using the docker-compose.yaml file (Figure 46) available in the AI4PublicPolicy gitlab repository of the Policy Linking component (<https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking/-/blob/main/docker/docker->

⁸ https://hub.docker.com/_/solr

[compose.yml](#)). Once the user has downloaded the docker-compose.yml file, he/she has to configure the Dataset and Policy Management database environment variables from the policy-linking service.

```

1 version: '3'
2 services:
3   solr:
4     image: solr
5     container_name: solr
6     ports:
7       - "9983:9983"
8       - "8983:8983"
9     volumes:
10      - data:/opt/solr/server/solr/mycores
11     entrypoint:
12       - docker-entrypoint.sh
13       - solr
14       - start
15       - -c
16       - -f
17   policy-linking:
18     image: registry.gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking:1.0.0
19     container_name: policy-linking
20     ports:
21       - "54758:8080"
22     environment:
23       - DB_HOST=${DATASET_POLICY_MANAGEMENT_DATABASE_IP_PORT}
24       - DB_USER=${DATASET_POLICY_MANAGEMENT_DATABASE_USER}
25       - DB_PSWD=${DATASET_POLICY_MANAGEMENT_DATABASE_PASSWORD}
26       - DB_NAME=POLICY
27       - SOLR_HOST=solr:8983
28     volumes:
29       data:
30

```

Figure 46. Policy Linking docker-compose.yml file

The following command has to be executed to run both containers, the one with Solr and the policy-linking one.

```
$ docker-compose up -d
```

Once the services are running in its own containers the Solr user interface is available at <http://localhost:8983/solr>(Figure 47), and the Policy Linking swagger interface is available at: <http://localhost:54758/policyLinking/ui> (Figure 48).

Figure 47: Docker version Solr ui

Figure 48. Docker version Policy Linking ui

To configure and initialize the policyLinking collection in Solr there is a bash script available in the Gitlab repository, <https://gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking/-/blob/main/policySchema.sh>. This bash script creates the policyLinking collection, defines the schema and uploads the actual existing policies. Then this command has to be executed:

```
$ ./policySchema.sh
```

5.2.2 Kubernetes version

A secret to store the Policy Linking gitlab registry credentials and allow Kubernetes to download the Policy Linking image is needed.

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```
$ kubectl create secret docker-registry ai4pp-policylinking-secret --docker-  
server=registry.gitlab.com/ai4publicpolicy/components/wp3/t3.4/policylinking  
--docker-username=<your-name> --docker-password=<your-pword> --docker-  
email=<your-email>
```

Next, the user creates the volume where Solr will persist the data. The `data-persistentvolumeclaim.yaml` file provides the `PersistentVolumeClaim` Kubernetes manifest to create the volume, to do that the user runs the following command:

```
$ kubectl apply -f data-persistentvolumeclaim.yaml
```

At this point the user can run the Solr pod running the following command and create the service to expose the solr user interface out of the Kubernetes cluster:

```
$ kubectl apply -f solr-deployment.yaml  
$ kubectl expose deployment solr --type=NodePort --name=solr-service
```

Once Solr is running, the policy linking component can be deployed. First the user configures the environment variables to connect to the Dataset and Policy Management component database and then, the following commands to deploy the policy linking component and to expose the policy linking swagger REST API interface out of the cluster Kubernetes must be executed:

```
$ kubectl apply -f policy-linking-deployment.yaml  
$ kubectl expose deployment policy-linking --type=NodePort --name=policy-linking-  
service
```

The endpoints for both Solr and the policy linking user interfaces can be obtained listing the pods and services:

```
$ kubectl get pods -o wide | grep solr  
solr-6b8b4f65ff-lflgj          1/1      Running    0  
23h      10.150.2.104      blade148  <none>    <none>  
$ kubectl get pods -o wide | grep policy-linking  
policy-linking-7985c58868-xsxkb 1/1      Running    0  
5m55s    10.150.2.106      blade148  <none>    <none>  
$ kubectl get svc | grep solr  
solr-service                    NodePort  10.101.100.168  <none>  
9983:32616/TCP,8983:30361/TCP  16m  
$ kubectl get svc | grep policy-linking  
policy-linking-service          NodePort  10.103.137.237  <none>  
8080:30833/TCP                  5m37s
```

In this case both pods are running in host blade148 (192.168.1.248) in ports 30361 and 30833, respectively as shown in Figure 49 and Figure 50.

Figure 49. Kubernetes distribution of Solr UI

Figure 50. Kubernetes distribution of Policy Linking REST API

6 Conclusions

This deliverable is the first version of the component for sharing and linking policies. This component has two main goals the reuse of policies and datasets and the linking of policies. The former is achieved by providing translation facilities among different languages and making this information available through the catalogue. The linking of policies is done by the user, selecting the policies that share common KPIs, objectives, description or datasets. In order to retrieve the candidate

policies natural language processing tools are used. This component is integrated with the Datasets and Policy Management component and available from the same web.

A new version of this deliverable is foreseen which will incorporate suggestions from the AI4PublicPolicy pilots will be incorporated as well as new features for showing visually the relation among different policies and possible clusters. The processing of natural language will consider synonyms and lemmatization of both verbs and nouns for more precise searches.